

Continuous iontronic chemotherapy reduces brain tumor growth in embryonic avian *in vivo* models

Verena Handl ^{a,1}, Linda Waldherr ^{a,b,1}, Theresia Arbring Sjöström ^{c,1}, Tobias Abrahamsson ^c, Maria Seitaniidou ^c, Sabine Erschen ^a, Astrid Gorischek ^a, Iwona Bernacka-Wojcik ^c, Helena Saarela ^c, Tamara Tomin ^d, Sophie Elisabeth Honeder ^{d,e}, Joachim Distl ^a, Waltraud Huber ^f, Martin Asslaber ^e, Ruth Birner-Grünberger ^{d,e}, Ute Schäfer ^g, Magnus Berggren ^c, Rainer Schindl ^{a,b,*}, Silke Patz ^{g,*}, Daniel T. Simon ^{c,*}, Nassim Ghaffari-Tabrizi-Wizsy ^{f,*}

^a Gottfried Schatz Research Center – Medical Physics and Biophysics, Medical University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

^b BioTechMed-Graz, Austria, Auenbruggerplatz 30, 8036 Graz, Austria

^c Laboratory of Organic Electronics, Department of Science and Technology, Linköping University, 60174 Norrköping, Sweden

^d Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, Technische Universität Wien, 1060 Vienna, Austria

^e Diagnostic and Research Institute of Pathology, Medical University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

^f Otto Loewi Research Center, Division of Immunology, Research Unit CAM Lab, Medical University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

^g Research Unit for Experimental Neurotraumatology, Medical University of Graz, 8010 Graz, Austria

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ABSTRACT

Local and long-lasting administration of potent chemotherapeutics is a promising therapeutic intervention to increase the efficiency of chemotherapy of hard-to-treat tumors such as the most lethal brain tumors, glioblastomas (GBM). However, despite high toxicity for GBM cells, potent chemotherapeutics such as gemcitabine (Gem) cannot be widely implemented as they do not efficiently cross the blood brain barrier (BBB). As an alternative method for continuous administration of Gem, we here operate freestanding iontronic pumps – “GemIPs” – equipped with a custom-synthesized ion exchange membrane (IEM) to treat a GBM tumor in an avian embryonic *in vivo* system. We compare GemIP treatment effects with a topical metronomic treatment and observe that a remarkable growth inhibition was only achieved with steady dosing *via* GemIPs. Daily topical drug administration (at the maximum dosage that was not lethal for the embryonic host organism) did not decrease tumor sizes, while both treatment regimes caused S-phase cell cycle arrest and apoptosis. We hypothesize that the pharmacodynamic effects generate different intratumoral drug concentration profiles for each technique, which causes this difference in outcome. We created a digital model of the experiment, which proposes a fast decay in the local drug concentration for the topical daily treatment, but a long-lasting high local concentration of Gem close to the tumor area with GemIPs. Continuous chemotherapy with iontronic devices opens new possibilities in cancer treatment: the long-lasting and highly local dosing of clinically available, potent chemotherapeutics to greatly enhance treatment efficiency without systemic side-effects.

Significance statement: Iontronic pumps (GemIPs) provide continuous and localized administration of the chemotherapeutic gemcitabine (Gem) for treating glioblastoma *in vivo*. By generating high and constant drug concentrations near the vascularized growing tumor, GemIPs offer an efficient and less harmful alternative to systemic administration. Continuous GemIP dosing resulted in remarkable growth inhibition, superior to daily topical Gem application at higher doses. Our digital modelling shows the advantages of iontronic chemotherapy in overcoming limitations of burst release and transient concentration profiles, and providing precise control over dosing profiles and local distribution. This technology holds promise for future implants, could

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: rainer.schindl@medunigraz.at (R. Schindl), silke.patz@medunigraz.at (S. Patz), daniel.simon@liu.se (D.T. Simon), nassim.ghaffari@medunigraz.at (N. Ghaffari-Tabrizi-Wizsy).

¹ Co-first authors.

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revolutionize treatment strategies, and offers a new platform for studying the influence of timing and dosing dependencies of already-established drugs in the fight against hard-to-treat tumors.

1. Introduction

1.1. Local chemotherapy approaches for GBM treatment

Chemotherapy relying on cytotoxins and targeted drugs is a powerful tool to intervene in tumor progression and plays a vital role in clinical tumor management [1,2]. Efficiency of a chemotherapeutic regime strongly depends on the choice of the therapeutic, as well as the timing and dosing profiles of the medication [3–5]. Local therapeutic regimes offer the possibility to administer high concentrations of selected drugs at controlled times, thus increasing their efficiency while simultaneously lowering systemic burden and associated side effects. Hence, radically new local therapeutic regimes, especially for hard-to-treat tumors such as pancreatic adenocarcinoma, soft tissue sarcomas, and GBM, have the potential to substantially improve therapeutic outcomes. New drug delivery strategies including drug-loaded scaffolds and externally controllable drug delivery devices have been developed in order to exploit these benefits [6–8]. In the case of GBM, a local drug release system could be beneficial because of the high local recurrence rate of GBM. Tumors recur within an area of 3 cm around the resection margins in almost every case [9–11], which causes an overall survival prognosis of only 15 months [12,13]. In addition, the BBB hinders many potent chemotherapeutics from reaching the cancerous tissue, limiting chemotherapy almost exclusively to the BBB-passing drug temozolomide (TMZ). Unfortunately, however, approx. 50% of GBM patients develop drug resistance to TMZ [14]. These facts suggest a local cancer therapy with alternative chemotherapeutics as a favorable method to intervene with this rapidly growing type of tumor [8]. Several local treatment technologies have been developed and are partially used in the clinical setting, including convection-enhanced delivery (CED) of targeted cytotoxins [15–17], laser interstitial thermal therapy, tumor treating fields (TTFs) [18], immunotherapy [19], opening the BBB with electroporation [20,21] or high-intensity focused ultrasound [22,23], as well as using drug-loaded scaffolds such as Gliadel or Cerebrac wafers [24,25].

Among local drug delivery methods, CED has become one of the most prominent methods to administer otherwise BBB-restricted therapies *via* injections to the target tissue in the brain. This offers the advantage of accumulating high local concentrations of the administered therapeutics and therefore increased treatment efficiency, and at the same time, reduced systemic toxicity. In parallel, iontophoretic tools have been shown to be able to generate high drug concentrations in the tumor and induce anti-tumor effects, while maintaining low systemic concentrations [26,27]. Currently, iontophoretic tools for chemotherapy are applied predominantly for transdermal drug administration and intravesical delivery. Besides the clinical success of these local drug delivery methods, both CED and iontophoretic systems leave much room for improvement for brain tumor treatment. In the case of iontophoresis, the technology relies on electric potential gradients to generate a combination of electrophoretic and electroosmotic drug delivery, and thus a mix of diffusional drug delivery and volume infusion. To reach effective delivery, devices are usually operated in the milliamperage range [27], which could potentially lead to unwanted muscle contractions and paresthesia when applied in the brain [28]. For safe operation, the generated pressure gradients from the volume infusion must be small and carefully monitored. This is an issue that is shared with the CED technique. CED can also, due to high flow rates and huge infusate volumes, cause complications due to backflow along the cannulas [29–31] (*i.e.*, fluid flowing “back up” along the outside of the cannula rather than into the intended target tissue). Also, CED requires complex time- and personnel-consuming clinical protocols and is limited to the duration of

the neurosurgery itself, which promoted CED to become predominantly a tool for clinical studies rather than an administration method for long-lasting GBM chemotherapy.

In this work we use a high precision and electronically controlled drug delivery technology that does not generate increased pressure, nor require high currents: organic electronic iontronic pumps. These “iontronic” pumps are devices that can be used for the controllable electromigration of charged molecules through an IEM [32]. We recently used a free-standing iontronic pump to deliver the chemotherapeutic Gem *in vitro* [33]. Gem is a potent chemotherapeutic and standard of care for different solid tumors, however, for GBM unused so far because of its BBB impermeability. It has been shown by us and others, that Gem itself however strongly affects proliferating tumor cells, while leaving neural tissue unaffected at therapeutic concentrations [33–35]. In the present work, we use a GemIP device with an anionically-functionalized hyperbranched polyglycerol (A-HPG) IEM [36]. Unlike our previous studies, which relied on stochastically organized linear polyelectrolytes to form the IEM, the hyperbranched structure of the A-HPG membrane allows for rational designs and optimization for high ionic conductivity. Its high stability is achieved by carefully balancing fixed charged groups in hydrophilic regions and stabilizing hydrophobic regions. First, we test GemIP performance *in situ*, followed by a characterization in an avian embryonic *in vivo* model. This model, also known as the chick chorioallantoic membrane (CAM) model, is a well-established model to study tumor proliferation, migration, and invasion *in vivo* [37,38]. The CAM model provides a preclinical miniature oncological model capable of evaluating tumorigenesis after therapeutic intervention, representing an intermediate model to bridge developmental hurdles between *in vitro* cell culture settings and rodent models. Engrafted CAM tumors are equipped with a rich vascularization and assemble into a three-dimensional tumor morphology, which provides an excellent model environment to observe tumor growth and pharmacodynamics – and to test bioelectronic drug delivery systems [38–40].

We hypothesized that a continuous dosing of Gem *via* an iontronic pump (GemIP) would interfere with GBM tumor growth significantly and causes relevant anti-tumor effects. We operated the GemIPs in close proximity to CAM-grown GBM tumors and compared the treatment performance with topical metronomic administration of Gem. In addition to experimental readouts evaluating tumor biology and drug accumulation, we use numerical models to simulate the drug concentration profiles for both transient and continuous treatment methods in a virtual CAM environment. Combining the *in situ* and *in vivo* experiments with the *in silico* models intertwines GemIP stimulation profiles with treatment performance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis of A-HPG and fabrication of GemIPs

All the commercial chemicals were used as received without any further purification. Bruno Bock Chemische Fabrik GmbH & Co. KG donated the chemical Thiocure 333 (ethoxylated trimethylolpropane tris(3-mercaptopropionate)). The A-HPG polyelectrolyte membrane material was synthesized as previously described by Abrahamsson et al. [36] HPG starting material (M_w : 10000–12,000 Da, D_M : 1.0–2.4, DB: 50–60%) functionalized with sodium 1-butanedisulfonate (80%) as fixed anionic charge groups and allyl groups (20%) for UV cross-linking capability [41]. Devices were fabricated as previously described [42]. Briefly, glass and polyimide-coated glass capillaries (25 & 50 μ m inner diameter) were filled with an IEM solution consisting of A-HPG (200 mg), Thiocure 333 (83 mg), 2-hydroxy-1-[4-(2-hydroxyethoxy)phenyl]-

2-methylpropan-1-one (2 mg) in methanol (347 μL) and water (250 μL). The glass capillaries filled with IEM solution were photo-exposed at 254 nm for 1 h, while polyimide-coated counter-parts were photo-exposed at 365 nm for 24–67 h. The capillaries were then cut into individual sections of 15 mm in length, embedded in a heat shrink tube and stored in 10 mM KCl solution. As electrodes, Ag/AgCl wires were used, the reference electrode was operated in a pipette tip filled with 4 w% Agar in 3 M KCl (agar bridge). Devices were operated via an in-house developed Arduino-based voltmeter.

2.2. GemIP operation and determination of fixed charges and delivery rates

As described previously by Waldherr et al. [33], a solution of 100 mM Gem(aq) at pH 4 was placed in the GemIP source reservoir and devices were operated at 25–100 nA (depending on device geometry, limited to 5 V) using custom Arduino-based devices. The channel loading was performed at 50 nA, indicated by increasing voltage over time, which reached a steady state value at which the channel was considered fully loaded with Gem, and devices were deemed ready for further experiments. Delivery rates were determined by operating GemIPs in a target volume of deionized water, PBS or 120 mM NaCl(aq). After operation, Gem concentration was measured via absorption at 267 nm with a NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The pH of the target solutions was measured under stirring using an HI 221 pH/ORP meter (Hanna Instruments, Germany) connected to an XS Sensor Micro S7 pH electrode (XS Instruments, Italy).

2.3. Computational models

Estimation and visualization of the delivery and distribution of Gem was done using finite element models in COMSOL Multiphysics v6.1. Three models were implemented in total: one device model for characterization and parameter tuning in simulated PBS (Fig. 1F, Suppl. Fig. 1), and two to represent and compare the two treatment methods (topical droplet (Suppl. Fig. 1) and GemIP administration (Fig. 2D, Suppl. Fig. 1), both on CAM). The topical droplet administration model was executed using the “transport of diluted species” interface, where the diffusional flux (J_{diff}) and distribution of Gem was simulated using Fick’s law:

$$\vec{J}_i = -D_i^* \vec{\nabla} c_i \quad (1)$$

where D_i^* is the effective diffusion coefficient and c_i is the concentration for species i . The effective diffusion coefficient is dependent on the media and is here implemented as the free diffusion coefficient D_i proportionally scaled with the mobility correction parameter fD_j for each media j :

$$D_i^* = fD_j D_i \quad (2)$$

The free diffusion coefficients are based on literature and listed in Suppl. Table 1. This topical droplet model was divided into three domains: the droplet, the CAM, and the liquid that has been punctuated beneath the tumor. For D_{Gem} , we approximate the diffusion coefficient of cytidine monophosphate, which is a structurally similar large organic ion and therefore smaller than the coefficients for small ions such as Na^+ , H^+ , or Cl^- [43]. The diffusivity is assumed to be equal to diffusion in water ($fD_{\text{water}} = 1$) in the droplet and in the liquid under the CAM. According to the results of Tay et al., we approximate the scaling of mobility through the dense CAM in comparison to water to $fD_{\text{CAM}} = 0.1$ for all species [44].

The model of GemIP in electrolyte and GemIP in CAM were simulated using the “tertiary current distribution” interface. In these models, the source electrolyte and IEM are added as domains. The Nernst-Planck equation (Eq. (3)) adds a migrational flux to numerically solve the distribution of ion concentrations as well as electric potential (ϕ) gradients

in the model. In all simulations, we assume no convective contribution to the ionic transport:

$$\vec{J}_i = -D_i^* \vec{\nabla} c_i - \frac{z_i F}{RT} D_i^* c_i \vec{\nabla} \phi \quad (3)$$

The ionic species included in the GemIP model are reduced to Gem^+ , H^+ , Na^+ , and Cl^- . The mobility of ions in the IEMs is also assumed to scale directly with their mobility in water. A commonly used assumption is that the mobility of ions in an IEM is approximately $0.1 \times$ lower than in water [45,46]. This assumption is thus not accounting for the contribution of the size of the charged molecules present, resulting in a misleading scaling when ions of various size are presents simultaneously. In addition, in highly conductive ion conductors such as A-HPG, a higher mobility is expected, especially for smaller ions [36]. For a more accurate representation of delivery efficiency in these experimental conditions, we instead relied on the mean delivery rates of Gem^+ , H^+ , and the resistance measured from GemIPs operated in a target of 120 mM NaCl(aq) (delivery rates listed in Suppl. Table 2, 50 μm inner diameter, target volume 200 μL , temperature 293.25 K) to estimate mobility correction parameters (fD) for each of the ions present in this specific IEM. The transport of Na^+ and Cl^- ions was not measured. Instead, the mobility correction factor for of the target cation Na^+ was set to a fixed value, since the influence is expected to be minor. The mobility correction factor of Cl^- was left for the model to tune to represent the remaining current that is not carried by Gem^+ or H^+ , neglecting any other parasitic currents or contributions from ions not implemented in the model. The parametric tuning was performed using an optimization step (SNOPT) in COMSOL Multiphysics, allowing for transport correction between a factor of 0.01 and 1. The simulated delivery rate data was collected in the IEM domain in the model at a distance of 1 μm from the outlet by a surface integral of the flux rates. The parametric optimization resulted in mobility correction parameters $fD_{\text{IEM,Gem}} = 0.12$, $fD_{\text{IEM,H}} = 0.56$, and $fD_{\text{IEM,Cl}} = 0.98$ (all listed in Suppl. Table 1). The low influence of the Na^+ mobility correction in forward bias was confirmed by the model, as the parametric values for the main current carriers (Gem^+ , H^+ and Cl^-) did not significantly change $fD_{\text{IEM,Na}}$ in the range 0.1–1. In remaining simulations, $fD_{\text{IEM,Na}}$ was set to 0.1. An electroneutrality assumption ($\sum z_i c_i = 0$) is added throughout the model. This assumption is considered valid in the bulk of the domains, but not within the nonlinear distribution of charges near the IEM-electrolyte interface [47]. To compensate for this, the Donnan potential is calculated by assuming the combined electrochemical potential equal on each side of the interface. Within the limiting current regime, where concentrations near the interface are relatively large, the non-electroneutral region is restricted to only a few nanometers from the interface. We consider this approach reasonable as long as the GemIP is operated within the limiting current regime. The model does not account for loss of drug post-release, thus the presented concentration estimations should be interpreted as the maximum dose each of these techniques can provide within the investigated areas.

2.4. Cell culture

The human GBM cell line U-87 (provided by MUG cell bank) was cultured at 37 °C and 5% CO_2 in Dulbecco’s Modified Eagle Medium (D-MEM) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 4.5 g/L glucose, 2 mM L-glutamine, and 1% MEM Non-Essential Amino Acids. U-251 MG cells were cultivated in D-MEM supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine and 10% FBS. All media and supplements were obtained from Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA. Primary neurons were freshly isolated from neonatal rat brain. Briefly, 4 cortical hemispheres were quickly removed from two PO-P1 rat pups (sacrificed by decapitation), washed with phosphate buffer, crosswise-chopped in 100 μm squares (McIlwain Tissue Chopper, Campden Instruments LTD, UK), and transferred to 1 mL Accutase for 20 min at 37 °C. Enzymatic digestion was stopped by addition of serum-containing medium. The suspension was then filtered through a 0.4 μm

(caption on next page)

Fig. 1. Experimental setup and GemIP characterization. **A:** GemIP installed on a U87-tumor grown on the CAM of a chick embryo. The silicone ring serves as a restriction margin when cells are seeded. Electrical contacts are not installed in this picture. **B:** Schematic of the channel filled with the A-HPG IEM. The IEM is embedded in a glass capillary with 25 or 50 μm inner diameter. **C–D:** Voltage traces for loaded GemIPs during operation at steady current. The devices with 25 μm ID were operated at 25 and 50 nA (C), and devices with 50 μm ID were operated at 50 and 100 nA (D). **E:** The delivery rates of Gem⁺ and H⁺ of a GemIP with 50 μm ID at 0, 50, and 100 nA. **F:** Simulation environment of a digital GemIP, mimicking experimental conditions (axially symmetric). **G:** Average ion concentrations in the channel for stationary simulations at different currents. **H:** Experimental delivery rates of Gem with GemIPs (50 μm ID) and corresponding data of the simulated device that were consecutively addressed with 50–0–50–0 nA (on 7 h – off 16 h – on 8 h – off 16 h). **I:** Mean voltage curve of a re-filling phase in 50 μm IEM devices operated at 50 nA after an “off” phase, which shows the re-filling with Gem (data shown as mean \pm SD, $n = 8$). **J:** Simulation of the loading state of the channel going from fully loaded at the start of the simulation experiment, to sequentially un-loading and re-filling during the 50–0–50–0 nA (on – off – on – off) sequence from part H. **K:** Simulation of the dynamic changes of the Gem⁺ delivery rates during the same operation protocol.

Fig. 2. Pharmacokinetics of Gem in GBM tumors grown on the CAM assay. **A:** Comparison of GemIP delivery rates pre- and post-operation of GemIPs for 72 and 120 h on CAM at 100 nA. **B:** Correlation of detected intratumoral Gem concentration vs. theoretically calculated Gem delivery in GBM tumors. Light pink data points (circles) represent devices that did not operate the whole time, black triangles represent devices that operated the whole experiment time from EDD12–15 (devices 4, 5, 7, 8, 9). Simple linear regression equation: $Y = 0.05446x + 0.6804$, $R^2 = 0.5905$. **C:** Schematic of the pharmacokinetic observation experiments in the CAM assay. Gem was administered *via* GemIP at 100 nA for 60 h, or *via* topical treatment (10 mM, 10 μL). Tissue (1 = tumor, 2 = liquid under the tumor, 3 = liquid in the amniotic cavity) was harvested after 1, 3, 6, or 24 h, cytosolic Gem was then extracted and quantified *via* MS. **D:** Quantification of Gem in tumor and in liquid under the tumor/amniotic cavity after 1, 3, 6, and 24 h after topical treatment with 10 mM Gem and after 60 h operation of GemIP at 100 nA. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

cell strainer and centrifuged for 5 min at 300 $\times g$. For cultivation of neurons, cells were re-suspended in cultivation medium: Neurobasal A Medium supplemented with 1% B-27, 0.5 mM GlutaMAX (all Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), 5 ng/mL β -FGF, 20 ng/mL EGF (both PrePro Tech, USA), and containing 0.2% Normocin (Invivogen, USA). After 4 days, β -FGF concentration was increased to 10 ng/mL.

For CAM assays, cells were cultured in T175 tissue culture flasks with canted neck and filter caps for adherent cells (Sarstedt AG & Co. KG, Germany). Media was changed every 3–4 days, and splitting was performed at 80% confluency in a 1:4 ratio. For cell splitting and CAM assays, cells were detached with TrypLE Express (Gibco, Denmark). Counting was performed using a hemocytometer (Assistent, Germany).

An amount of 10^6 cells were calculated for each CAM onplant and an appropriate volume was removed from the cell suspension, which was transferred into a 50 mL centrifuge tube (Sarstedt AG & Co. KG, Germany) and gently centrifuged down (1000 rpm, 5 min). For one onplant, 10^6 cells were resuspended in 15 μL PBS and 5 μL Geltrex (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) to receive a total amount of 20 μL per onplant. The mastermix was kept on ice until CAM assay procedure.

2.5. Proteomics analysis

U251 glioblastoma cells (in quadruplicates) were treated for 48 h with 1 μM Gem or vehicle, before being harvested for proteomics

analysis. To comparatively check if Gem has any detrimental effect on neurons, primary rat neurons (also $n = 4$ per condition) were treated for 72 h with 1 mM Gem (1000× higher concentration) and as well harvested for proteomics analysis. Cells were lysed in 100 μL of 100 mM Tris (pH = 8.5) containing 1% sodium dodecylsulphate (SDS), 10 mM tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine, and 40 mM chloroacetamide with a 2×5 s sonication cycle at 10% amplitude, upon which 20 μg protein per each sample was acetone precipitated overnight at -20°C . The following day, proteins were dissolved in 25% trifluoroethanol in 100 mM Tris (pH = 8.5), then diluted to 10% TFE with 100 mM ammonium bicarbonate and digested overnight with trypsin (1:50 trypsin to protein ratio). Consequently, 4 μg of the digest was offline desalted using in-house-made stage tips, and around 300 ng per sample was used for liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) analysis. Chromatography was carried out on an Ultimate 3000 RCS Nano Dionex system equipped with an Ionopticks Aurora Series UHPLC C18 column (250 mm \times 75 μm , 1.6 μm) (Ionopticks, Australia). Solvent A was 0.1% formic acid in water and solvent B acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid. Total LC-MS/MS run per sample was 86.5 min with the following gradient: 0–5.5 min: 2% B; 5.5–25.5 min: 2–10% B; 25.5–45.5 min: 10–25% B; 45.5–55.5 min: 25–37% B; 55.5–85.5 min: 37–80% B; 65.5–75.5 min: 80% B; 75.5–76.5 min: 80–2% B; 76.5–86.5: 2% B at a flow rate of 400 nL/min and 40°C . The timsTOF mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Germany) was operated in positive mode with enabled trapped ion mobility spectrometry (TIMS) at 100% duty cycle (100 ms ramp and accumulation time). Source capillary voltage was set to 1400 V and dry gas flow to 3 L/min at 180°C . For U251 cells, the scan mode was set to parallel accumulation-serial fragmentation (PASEF) for the scan range of 100–1700 m/z . Precursor selection was based on their intensity (data-dependent acquisition) and the precursors were allowed to accumulate for the total of four ramps per PASEF cycle, bringing the total cycle time to 0.53 s. For neuron samples, scanning mode was set to data-independent PASEF (diaPASEF), with defined $32 \times 26 m/z$ isolation windows from m/z 400 to 1200, with a 1 m/z overlap between the windows. Raw files from the glioblastoma cells were analyzed using MaxQuant software (v1.6.17.0) [48], while rat neurons were processed in DIA-NN (v. 1.7.13 beta 12) [49]. The SwissProt human proteome database in FASTA format (containing common contaminants; downloaded on 2019-04-16, 20,467 sequences) was used for U251 cells, while rat FASTA (downloaded on 2021-03-22, 8118 entries) was used for library-free spectral matching of rat neurons. The maximum number of trypsin mis-cleavages was set to 2 in MaxQuant and to 1 in DIA-NN. Cysteine carbamidomethylation was set as a fixed while methionine oxidation as a variable modification in both software. The resulting matrix of quantified proteins (4113 for U251 and 2884 for neurons, respectively) was then imported into Perseus (v1.6.14.0) [50], where the values were log2 transformed, and filtered for valid values in at least three replicates of one group (Gem or control). This reduced the matrix to 2661 (U251) or 2112 proteins (neurons), and residual missing values were imputed from a normal distribution (down shift 1.8, width 0.3). Student's t -tests were carried out on these resulting tables (with false discovery rate (FDR) corrected p-value < 0.05 ; $S_0 = 0.1$). The raw data from this experiment, including the FASTA files, MaxQuant, and DIA-NN outputs have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the PRIDE [51,52] partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD040209.

2.6. Ex ovo CAM assay

Fertilized white Lohmann eggs were disinfected and incubated for three days at 37.6°C and 40–60% humidity. At embryonal development day (EDD) 3, eggs were cracked into a plastic petri dish using an electrical blade and again incubated at the same conditions for another 7 days. Either on EDD9 or EDD10 autoclaved silicone rings were placed on the CAM and 20 μL cell suspension (10^6 cells) was pipetted in the center of the silicone rings. On EDD10, loaded GemIPs were installed on the

tumors with the channel outlet in close vicinity to the tumor or contacting it. GemIPs were operated at 100 nA for up to 120 h. Topical treatment was done daily with different concentrations and frequencies. In order to result at a total Gem amount of 5 nmol, a daily single drop (10 μL) of 100 μM Gem/PBS was placed over five days. Analogously, this was done for 50 nmol (daily 10 μL , 1 mM), 100 nmol (daily 10 μL , 2 mM), 250 nmol (daily 10 μL , 5 mM), 500 nmol (daily 10 μL , 10 mM), and 1000 nmol ($5 \times 20 \mu\text{L}$ per day, daily, 2 mM). After treatment, the tumors were microscopically documented and xenografts were excised out of the pre-cooled eggs, and transferred into PBS. Embryos were kept on ice and sacrificed by decapitation. At this point, tumors were either snap frozen in liquid N_2 for mass spectrometric (MS) analysis, digested into single cells for flow cytometry, or fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) overnight for histology. Fixated tumors were dehydrated via an ascended alcohol series, starting with 70% ethanol up to 100% ethanol and toluene followed by xenograft embedding into paraffin for histology and immunohistochemical analyses.

2.7. MS quantification of Gem in CAM specimen

Tumors were harvested and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C . To collect the liquid under the tumors, the CAM was punctuated using a needle and 1.2 mL of the liquid under the tumor was collected. To both tumors and CAM liquid, 80% MeOH (20:80 with H_2O , kept at -20°C) was added, tumors were homogenized using a dispensing wand (Ultra-Turrax), and samples were kept at -20°C for 20 min. Afterwards, extracts were centrifuged for 10 min at 14,000 rpm, 4°C and the supernatant was dried under nitrogen flow. Tumor extracts were resolubilized in 50 μL 0.1% formic acid in water and tumor extracts were measured as previously described [33]. CAM liquid extracts were dissolved in 100 μL water but were however subjected to another cleaning step using 200 μL methanol and 50 μL chloroform. Polar fractions were then re-collected to new tubes, dried, and resuspended in 50 μL water prior being subjected to liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry analysis. For CAM liquids, consequent Gem quantitation was carried out as previously described [33] with some adaptations. Namely, 10 μL of sample was injected into an LCMS-8060 system (Shimadzu, Japan) with the flow rate of 0.2 ml/min and following gradient: 0–3 min: 0% B, 3.01–7.00 min: 20% B, 7.01–9.00 min: 100% B, 9.01–14.00 min: 0% B (A being 0.1% formic acid; B 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile). MS was operated in positive mode, with gas flow of 2.5, 10, and 10 L/min for nebulizing, drying, and heating gas respectively. Desolation line temperature was set to 250°C and heat block temperature to 400°C . Transition parameters for Gem were $264 \rightarrow 112.5$ (CE -20) and $264 \rightarrow 95$ (CE -43). Peak integration was carried out in Shimadzu Postrun Analysis.

2.8. Conversion of human drug dose into human equivalent dose for CAM

Following Nair and Jacob [53], the human equivalent dose (HED) was calculated based on Eqs. (4) and (5):

$$HED \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}} \right] = \frac{\text{human dose} \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{m}^2} \right]}{K_m \left[\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \right]} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Gem dose for CAM} [\text{mmol}] = \frac{HED \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{kg}} \right] \times \text{body weight}_{\text{egg}} [\text{kg}]}{\text{molecular weight}_{\text{Gem}} \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{mmol}} \right]} \quad (5)$$

We assumed a human dose of 1250 mg/m^2 (Gemzar prescribing information, Ref. ID 3503046), correction factor $K_m = 37 \text{ kg/m}^2$, and egg body weight to be 0.05 kg. The molecular weight of Gem is 263.2 g/mol .

2.9. Histology and immunohistochemistry

Embedded tumors were cut by semi-automatic microtome (Leica RM2245 V2.4 rotary microtome, Leica Biosystems Nussloch GmbH, Germany) into 5 μm sections and transferred onto adhesion slides (SuperFrost Plus™ Adhesion Slides Eprelia™, USA). Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was performed after deparaffinization and dehydration of the tissue sections (xylene, decreasing ethanol series 100%–70%, 3 min each). Immunohistochemical staining was performed using UltraVision Quanto Detection System HRP (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Briefly, tissue sections were deparaffinized and dehydrated, as described above, followed by a citrate buffer antigen retrieval (pH 6) using a decloaking chamber NxGen (BioCare Medical, USA) at 95 °C for 10 min in the microwave. Next, specimens were incubated with 3% H_2O_2 dissolved in MeOH for 15 min to block endogenous peroxidase activity, followed by 3 washing steps in $1 \times \text{TBS-T}$. To prevent unspecific binding UltraVision Protein Block (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was applied on the specimen for 10 min. Thereafter, slides were immediately incubated with Cleaved Caspase-3 (Asp175) primary Antibody (9661, Cell Signaling Technology, Netherlands) using a 1:400 dilution in Antibody Diluent (OP Quanto, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) overnight at 4 °C. Detection steps were then carried out according to manufacturer's protocol (Dako Liquid DAB+ Substrate Chromogen System, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Immunohistochemical staining of Anti-human primary DAKO anti-Ki-67 antibody Clone MIB-1 (GA62661–2) was performed by the automated system DAKO OMNIS combined with DAKO OMNIS Flex HRP detection. Stained slides were scanned with a ScanScope AT System, using the associated software ScanScope Console. Evaluation of slides was performed by QuPath (Quantitative pathology & Bioimage Analysis, free software, funded from Invest Northern Ireland & Cancer Research UK accelerator). Positive cells were used to generate an index, from which the percentage of positively stained cells was generated. The erythrocyte count was assessed utilizing H&E staining, wherein the individual nuclei of erythrocytes were determined based on their distinct eosinophilic appearance. A 40 \times magnification facilitated by the ScanScope AT System, both central and marginal regions were randomly designated and quantified.

2.10. Flow cytometry

After excision, CAM tumors chosen for flow cytometric analysis were transferred into a digestion mix which contained 1 mL D-MEM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), 1% Gibco penicillin/streptomycin (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), 6 μL deoxyribonuclease I (40 U/mL), 15 μL collagen type I (50 U/mL), 15 μL collagen type II (50 U/mL), 15 μL collagen type IV (50 U/mL), and 3 μL elastase (0.075 U/mL). All enzymes were purchased from Worthington Biochemical (Lakewood, NJ, USA). This mix was kept on a thermo-block (37 °C) for 75 min. To ensure a gentle dissolving, up and down pipetting was carried out every 10 min. Afterwards, tumor cells were centrifuged for 4 min at 1000 rpm and washed twice with PBS. Washed cell pellet was resuspended in 500 μL PBS (cold) and subsequent fixated in 5 mL 70% EtOH (4 °C). Fixed cells were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 4 min and washed twice with 5 mL $1 \times \text{PBS}$ plus 0.5% FBS. Afterwards, cell pellets were resuspended in propidium iodide (PI) hypotonic lysis buffer and transferred into 5 mL round-bottom polystyrene tubes. The PI hypotonic lysis buffer contained 0.1% sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate, 0.1% Triton X-100, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ PI (Sigma Aldrich, USA), and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ RNase A (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) dissolved in deionized water. Subsequently, cells were incubated for 20 min before measurement. CytoFLEX S with CytExpert software (Beckman Coulter, Vienna, Austria) was used for flow cytometry measurement. Data was analyzed using ModFit LT software excluding aggregates and debris from the cellular components for optimization of histogram evaluation.

2.11. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using commercially available software (Prism 8, GraphPad, USA) and specific statistical tests were used as stated in the figure description.

3. Results

3.1. Electrically controlled delivery of Gem with A-HPGs

Iontronic delivery devices are based on IEM channels that allow variable design and materials. For this pioneer CAM-GBM tumor study, we chose a single channel design based on fused-silica capillaries with inner diameters (ID) of either 25 μm or 50 μm filled with an A-HPG IEM (Fig. 1A, B). These GemIPs were pre-evaluated for their delivery of K^+ cations (Suppl. Fig. 2), after which the source electrolyte was exchanged to 100 μL of 100 mM Gem(aq) at pH 4, a pH at which Gem is predicted to be protonated and therefore positively charged (strongest basic $\text{pK}_\text{A} = 3.65$).

The devices with 25 and 50 μm ID were then addressed at 50 nA, which resulted in a characteristic time-dependent “loading” voltage trace (representative traces for devices with 25 and 50 μm ID in Suppl. Fig. 3 and 4, respectively). At constant current, the corresponding voltage initially increased over time due to the replacement of K^+ by the larger, lower mobility Gem^+ cations, causing the increase of the channel resistivity. Once the voltage reached a steady state, the cation exchange was complete (*i.e.*, all fixed negative charges in the IEM compensated by Gem^+ or H^+), and Gem and H^+ were assumed to be steadily delivered through the A-HPG IEM. This approach clearly indicates the time point of a “ready to use” GemIP (Suppl. Fig. 3, 4). Depending on the ID, the devices can be addressed at up to 50 or 100 nA, as the operation was restricted to 5 V by our custom power source. Representative voltage traces for devices performing stable Gem delivery with 25 and 50 μm diameter at different addressing modes are shown in Fig. 1C and D, respectively, and the corresponding device characteristics for 25 and 50 μm ID GemIPs are shown in Suppl. Figs. 3 and 4. We observed that the mean steady voltage for devices with 25 μm addressed with 25 and 50 nA is almost three times higher than in devices with 50 μm IEM diameter (Suppl. Table 2 and Suppl. Fig. 5). The most critical characteristic of these devices is the delivery rate of Gem and the co-delivery rate of H^+ (Fig. 1E, for 50 μm ID devices). The total amount of H^+ co-delivered arises from a combination of ions present in the acidified source electrolyte, Gem^+ delivered, and potentially from additional water splitting [54]. Even though Gem^+ is a large and less mobile ion than H^+ , we measure predominately Gem^+ , likely due to the imbalance in the concentrations in the source electrolyte: 100 mM Gem^+ compared to 100 μM of H^+ (*i.e.*, pH 4) [55]. We observed comparable Gem delivery rates for GemIPs with 25 and 50 μm ID. However, the passive leakage from the 50 μm ID GemIPs is threefold higher than in the smaller ID devices (Suppl. Fig. 6).

In the long-term perspective, keeping track of the active delivery and passive leakage are of high relevance for generating reliable GemIP operation protocols. It is important to notice that the loading state is not stationary, but rather dynamic due to changes in the operation protocol. Consequently, the passive and active delivery will vary with loading state and driving current. To investigate the loading state and its dynamics more closely, we created a computational model of the GemIP in COMSOL Multiphysics (Fig. 1F). The model was based on the experimental concentrations and dimensions of the IEM (from Fig. 1D-E), which has a fixed charge concentration of 0.74 M, as previously reported [36], and the effective diffusion coefficients of the ions present in the IEM. The mobility of ions in the IEM was furthermore adjusted to experimental delivery numbers of Gem^+ and H^+ and yielded higher relative mobility for H^+ in comparison to Gem^+ (0.56 and 0.12 respectively, see methods section for details), yet H^+ delivery was low due to the abundance of Gem^+ ions in the source electrolyte. Stationary

simulations at different operation currents (Fig. 1G) show that a resting system equilibrates close to a 1:1 ratio between the counterion from the source (Gem^+), and the counterion from the target (Na^+). This equilibrium shifts to Gem^+ with applied current to fully loaded devices (Fig. 1G). These averaged values are also used as initial values in the time-dependent simulations, to mimic the “ready to use” state after loading. At 100 nA this equals approx. 750 mM Gem^+ , 20 mM Cl^- , 0.6 mM H^+ , and 8.9 mM Na^+ in the channel.

To investigate the dynamic on-off behavior of the GemIP, both *in situ* and *in silico*, we performed a consecutive on-off operation sequence: operation of loaded channels (50 μm ID) at 50 nA for 7 h (“on”), followed by 0 nA for 16 h (“off”), then 50 nA for 8 h, and finally 0 nA for 16 h. The delivery rates generated by the GemIP for each operation phase (light pink), as well as the corresponding simulated values, are plotted in Fig. 1H (dark pink). This experimental GemIP operation sequence was repeated in the computational representation of the setup to follow the GemIP’s loading state. Besides Gem^+ , other ions (Na^+ , H^+ , and Cl^-) are involved in these processes, which were taken into account in the simulations as well. Due to the passive diffusion of Gem^+ out of the channel, balanced with ion exchange *via* passive diffusion of Na^+ into the channel, the devices show a characteristic “refilling” phase when addressed at steady current after an “off” period (50 nA operation, voltage curve is presented as mean \pm SD in Fig. 1I). This refilling also manifested in a slightly reduced delivery rate of partially unloaded devices after a 16 h “off” period (Fig. 1H). The computational model was also used to estimate the dynamic changes of delivery rates and “loading state” of the channel. The varying flow rates during the on-off operation sequence can be followed in Fig. 1K and Suppl. Fig. 7. Note here that the passive leakage of the device is largest right after the device is turned off and decreases with time. The loading state, represented as the percentage of the different ions present in the IEM, can be seen in Fig. 1J. After 16 h, 75% of the channel is still loaded, while leakage is reduced by 93%. To summarize, the GemIP performance presented here (based on optimized and tunable dendritic A-HPG IEMs) shows a clear performance increase compared to our previous version (based on linear polyelectrolyte IEMs) [33], especially considering the threefold higher delivery rates (from 0.1 pmol/min/nA (at 20 nA) previously, to 0.3–0.4 pmol/min/nA here (at 50 and 100 nA, respectively). We thus deemed these devices ready for long-term operation of Gem delivery in a more challenging tumor model, that is the vascularized tumors in the *in vivo* CAM model.

3.2. Characterization of GemIP performance on vascularized glioblastoma tumors

Our primary aim was to test and evaluate GemIP performance *in vivo* by targeting vascularized GBM tumors cultivated on the CAM of a chick embryo, which fulfils the role of a “breathing organ” of the embryos. As described above, this assay allows the cultivation of vascularized tumors that can be used in experiments for up to a week (ethical guidelines foresee the end of these experiments at EDD15 [56]). We cultivated the human GBM cell line U-87 MG on the CAM on EDD9, which resulted in the formation of spherical tumors with up to 2 mm diameter within 72 h, a tumor that is 20–40 \times the size of the GemIP outlet (Suppl. Fig. 8). On EDD12 we installed the GemIPs on the visible tumors and operated them at 100 nA for 72 h (representative traces in Suppl. Fig. 9).

During the three days of GemIP operation on the CAM-tumors, some devices had a rapid increase in voltage until reaching the operational maximum of 5 V (Suppl. Fig. 9), indicating a source of unexpectedly high resistance somewhere in the GemIP circuit (either the electronic or ionic branch). To evaluate if this rapid operation loss was due to a disrupted electrical circuit when the GemIP outlet lost the contact with the CAM membrane or became too dry, we re-evaluated the individual delivery rate for each device after the CAM experiment (*post* CAM). We observed a reduction in the delivery rates of devices operated at 100 nA pre-CAM assay (replotted data from Fig. 1E) compared to devices post-CAM assay (Fig. 2A), as well as a bigger variance of the delivery rates

(median_{native} = 39.95 pmol/min; median_{post-72h CAM} = 21.80 pmol/min; median_{post-120h CAM} = 16.55 pmol/min). Nevertheless, the *post*-CAM assay delivery rates showed that the devices could still be used for functional drug delivery, however, less efficient and with broader variability. Apparently, the operation of GemIPs in a living host system is a stress test for the devices and shows that functional drug delivery strongly depends on a stable and conductive experimental setting. Our experiments suggest a tendency towards a reduced drug delivery rate when GemIPs are operated in a weakly hydrated *in vivo* system, which will influence the iontronic implant design for follow-up *in vivo* studies on CAM and in rodents.

3.3. GemIPs generate relevant drug concentrations that correlate with GemIP performance

Based on the individual *post*-CAM delivery rate of each device and the effective operation time, in which the devices had given a steady operation voltage while sourcing 100 nA (indicated with dashed line, 6–60 h, Suppl. Fig. 9), the theoretically delivered Gem was calculated. We set this in correlation to the intratumoral Gem amount that was quantified in the harvested GBM tumors with mass spectrometry. The correlation of theoretically delivered Gem vs. experimentally determined Gem is shown in Fig. 2B, where black data points indicate that the devices were functionally operating over the whole time (devices 4, 5, 7–9, Suppl. Fig. 9). The theoretically delivered and experimentally determined Gem amount in the tumor show a positive correlation (Pearson r coefficient = 0.77, p -value = 0.016).

It is noteworthy that the quantified Gem was orders of magnitude lower than the initially administered Gem (MS detected picomole amounts, while nanomoles were delivered, Fig. 2B, D). This is the case for both topical treatments (quantification after 1, 3, 6, and 24 h after Gem treatment) and the GemIP treated tumors (Fig. 2D). This difference in drug levels, independent from the administration technique, is possibly due to the integration of the drug into the DNA or due to efficient drug elimination processes. According to literature, the major pathway of drug distribution and clearance after a topical treatment is the removal of the drug *via* the vascularization of the CAM [38,57,58], as well as the fast incorporation into the DNA [59]. Other elimination pathways include diffusion, metabolism, and degradation.

We further evaluated the drug distribution effect by quantifying the drug accumulated after a topical Gem treatment of 100 nmol (single topical drop of 10 μL of 10 mM Gem) in the tumor and in the liquid volume under the tumor or the amniotic cavity at different time points after drug application (Fig. 2C). We observed a trend of a 10^3 – 10^4 fold lower concentration under the tumor or in the amniotic cavity compared to the corresponding time point in the tumor (Fig. 2D). This confirms that the major drug clearance pathway is not *via* diffusion through the CAM bilayer into the liquid under the tumor, but that the applied drug is cleared *via* the vasculature of the host organism, as suggested by literature. Both the correlation of GemIP operation and drug accumulation, as well as the drug rediscovery and distribution clearly show that GemIPs perform local chemo drug delivery into the tumor.

3.4. GemIPs arrest GBM tumor cells in the cell cycle

In order to evaluate the biological effects induced by GemIP treatment, we operated GemIPs on formed GBM tumors on the CAM for up three days at 100 nA. As positive controls we introduced metronomic topical treatments of 1 mM Gem, 10 μL per day (30 nmol in total, Fig. 3A). Gem is known to incorporate into the DNA of cells during replication. Once incorporated into the DNA, the drug inhibits the synthesis (S) phase of the cell cycle, and therefore hinders cells from entering the subsequent G2 phase of the cell cycle. This mechanism of action manifests in a decreased ratio of cells in the G2 phase following treatment with Gem (Fig. 3B) [60,61]. We quantified the cell cycle distribution of GemIP treated tumors and compared them to topical Gem

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Fig. 3. Operating GemIPs on CAM-grown GBM tumors. A: Time course and treatment schedule of the *ex ovo* CAM assay in chick embryos for the experiments in parts C–F. At EDD9, silicone rings are placed and 10^6 cells are placed into the ring (engraftment). The tumor forms within the next 72 h into a visible round tumor tissue, which is treated from EDD12–15 with either a GemIP operated at 100 nA or metronomic topical treatment (10 μ L, 1 mM Gem, daily). B: Schematic cell cycle arrest in the S phase induced by Gem treatment and the relevant peaks in a flow cytometry histogram to analyze cell cycle distributions. C: Histograms of the PI-staining for quantification of cells in the G2 phase of untreated cells (growth control), cells treated 3 \times topically with 1 mM Gem (30 nmol topical) or with a GemIP at 100 nA for 72 h (GemIP). D: Quantification of cells in the G2 phase after treatment. Statistical analysis is a Brown-Forsythe and Welch ANOVA with a *post hoc* Dunnett's T3 multiple comparisons test. ****: p-value <0.001, **: p-value <0.1. E: IHC of CAM tumors with anti-cleaved Caspase 3 antibody to quantify apoptosis induced by different treatment schedules. Scale bars in 5 \times = 200 μ m, in 40 \times = 20 μ m. F: Quantification of CC3 positive cells (brownish stained cells from Fig. E), Brown-Forsythe and Welch ANOVA with a *post hoc* Dunnett's T3 multiple comparisons test. ***: p-value <0.01, **: p-value <0.1. G: Volcano plot of U-251 MG cells comparing the proteome of untreated cells to the one of treated with 1 μ M Gem for 48 h. H: Volcano plot comparing the proteomes of primary neurons that are untreated with those treated with 1 mM Gem for 72 h ($n = 3$ –4 per group, FDR corrected p-value set to 0.05, $S_0 = 0.1$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

administration (daily dose of 1 mM Gem, 10 μ L per drop, three drops results in 30 nmol) by performing a PI staining of the DNA and quantifying the distribution of cells in the different cell cycles by flow cytometry (schematic description of expected peaks for G1/G2 and S phase shown in Fig. 3B, gate setting is shown in Suppl. Fig. 10). Untreated tumors yielded clear peaks of G1, S and G2 phase (Fig. 3C, growth control, pink square highlights the G2 phase). In comparison, the 30 nmol topical control (3 \times topical dose of 1 mM Gem) and GemIP-treated GBM tumors (theoretically *ca.* 89 nmol based on median *post*-CAM delivery rate of all devices in this experiment and 68 h operation time) showed a significantly diminished G2 phase peak (Fig. 3C). We quantified the percentage of cells in the G2 phase, which resulted in $3.9 \pm 1.7\%$ of cells in the G2 in the growth control, a completely abolished G2 phase in the positive control (topical treatment with 30 nmol Gem) and a significantly reduced G2 phase in the GemIP treated tumors ($1.3 \pm 1.2\%$, Fig. 3D).

3.5. GemIPs induce apoptosis in CAM GBM tumors

The potency of Gem in chemotherapy is its action to cause cell death primarily by inducing apoptosis [62,63]. Therefore, we aimed to quantify the rate of apoptosis in GemIP treated GBM tumors. Tumors were treated analogously to the treatment protocol for quantifying the cell cycle arrest (Fig. 3A, 72 h of 100 nA GemIP operation and 3 \times topical Gem, 1 mM). Afterwards, tumors were cut out and prepared for immunohistochemical analysis (sample preparation explained in Suppl. Fig. 11). The slides were stained with Cleaved Caspase-3 (CC3) antibody, which indicates early apoptotic areas in the tumor, and hematoxylin as counter stain for nuclei (Fig. 3E). This showed that both treatments with Gem (topical and GemIP) significantly induced CC3. In comparison to the growth control ($0.4 \pm 0.3\%$ positive cells), the rate of apoptosis was significantly upregulated in the positive control ($4.9 \pm 2.5\%$) and in the GemIP treated tumors ($3.8 \pm 3.9\%$, Fig. 3F). These experiments clearly indicate that GemIPs effectively induce cell cycle arrest as well as apoptosis in growing tumors.

3.6. Gem is a potent tumor killer, but does not influence the proteome of neuronal cultures

Since the ultimate aim for GemIP technology is to release the chemotherapeutic at locally high concentrations in the human brain, we were motivated to more deeply investigate the effects of Gem on neurons than previously studied [33]. Since Gem is usually not used for GBM therapy because of its BBB-restriction, which can be circumvented by the GemIP treatments, we want to carefully evaluate effects in the healthy and cancerous tissue [33–35]. In other words, how does GemIP treatment effect the “healthy cells” adjacent to the tumor? We therefore analyzed the proteomes of Gem-treated GBM cell line U-251 MG (1 μ M Gem for 48 h) and of neurons (1 mM Gem for 72 h) and compared them to their corresponding vehicle treated controls (Fig. 3G, H). As expected, our results indicate that the proteome of GBM cells is prominently altered upon Gem treatment. In fact, upon 48 h of 1 μ M Gem treatment the U-251 MG cells, even after a stringent statistical analysis (see

Materials and methods section), we observed that strikingly 829 proteins were significantly more and 1142 proteins significantly less abundant in Gem-treated GBM cells compared to the controls (Fig. 3G). We performed this experiment analogously in neurons, which were even treated with 1000 \times higher Gem concentration (1 mM and not only 1 μ M), and for a longer period of time (72 h *versus* 48 h for GBM cells), and saw that only three proteins of the neuronal proteome were significantly altered in the treatment group (Fig. 3H). Based on a literature search and to the best of our knowledge, the noted proteins did not suggest a role in apoptotic processes or processes related to Gem response.

3.7. Long-lasting GemIP operation interferes with tumor formation and growth

After successful implementation of GemIPs on already grown tumors, we investigated the role of GemIP treatment on tumor formation and subsequent proliferation. Among other factors, we presume that the therapeutic success of GemIPs will severely depend on the size and extent of cohesion of cells in a three-dimensional tumor. Hence, we hypothesize it will be most promising to interfere with tumor recurrence and growth when tumor cells are loosely associated but not yet tightly assembled in a three-dimensional tumor. In the context of treating a GBM patient, this will be the case after resection of the gross tumor mass, where the remaining tumor cell formations are rather isolated and infiltrate the brain. In this setting, the drug needs to interfere with those singular cell formations, but would not be required to penetrate dense three-dimensional tumor tissue. Thus, for clinical GemIP application we envision the placement and operation of the implant in the resulting cavity after resection of the gross tumor mass, targeting remaining solitary tumor cells that have infiltrated the healthy brain tissue. To investigate the influence of GemIP operation in a loosely assembled tumor architecture context, we started the GemIP treatment on EDD10, when tumors are still forming, and extended the treatment time to the maximum allowed in the CAM assay, 120 h, in which the GemIP was operated at 100 nA (Fig. 4A). The resulting mean voltage profile of five devices is shown in Fig. 4B. It is noteworthy that 44% of the devices did not operate the whole time due to loss of contact of device to tumor (movement or drying out on the CAM, as mentioned before), contact loss of electrodes, or potential device failure (reaching the max. voltage of 5 V, exemplary in Suppl. Fig. 12, only the case if the device also showed max. voltage in the *post*-CAM runs).

On the CAM, the rapid growth [64] and strong neo-vascularization [65] that is observed in GBM becomes noticeable when the U-87 MG GBM cell line was cultivated on it. We observed a remarkable gain in the tumor size of 0.9 ± 0.6 mm of U-87 MG tumor cells between the first day at which a visible tumor had formed (EDD12) and three days later at the end point of the experiment (EDD15, Fig. 4C). The pink hue of the tumor was also noteworthy, as it indicates strong vascularization, especially visible in advanced embryonic stages (Fig. 4C).

We introduced topical metronomic treatment controls, in which we treated the tumors every day by placing a 10 μ L drop of Gem at different concentrations in the silicone ring, a protocol mimicking the dosing profile of daily administration of chemotherapy (Fig. 4A). According to

(caption on next page)

Fig. 4. 120 h long-term GemIP treatment of GBM tumors grown on the CAM assay. A: time course and treatment schedule of the *ex ovo* CAM assay for the experiments in parts B–H. Cells are engrafted at EDD9, treatment with GemIP from EDD10–EDD15, or topical drug administration from EDD10–EDD14. At EDD15, tumors are harvested and follow-up analyzed. B: Mean \pm SD voltage of five representative GemIP devices operated on CAM for 120 h at 100 nA (50 μ m ID). C: Increase in diameter of an untreated U-87 MG tumor on CAM from EDD12 to EDD15 (encircled with dashed lines). Tumor cells assembled into a discrete tumor until EDD12. Until the last experiment day EDD15, tumors grew and became vascularized by the blood vessels of the chick embryo. D: Survival of chick embryos undergoing daily topical Gem treatment ranging from 0 to 1000 nmol, or GemIP treatment (119 nmol, $n = 6$ –14). E: Representative images of CAM-grown U-87 MG tumors without treatment (growth control and sham IP control), topical 100 nmol or 250 nmol treatment (max. Nontoxic dose), and with GemIP. F: Size analysis of U-87 MG tumors grown on CAM, upon topical and GemIP treatment. GC: growth control (0 nmol), IP ctrl: Ion pump control (0 nmol), 100 nmol topical, 250 nmol topical, GemIP (119 nmol, 100 nA, 120 h operation). Only significant results are indicated with asterisk. **: p-value = 0.0041 (Brown-Forsythe and Welch ANOVA and Dunnett's T3 multiple comparisons test). G: Quantification of CC3 positive cells, Kruskal-Wallis-test and Dunn's multiple comparison analysis. ***: p-value <0.001. H: H&E sections of GBM tumors among different treatment protocols. Two ROIs were selected (margin and center) and are shown below (blood vessels highlighted in pink and desaturated blue signal from hematoxylin). Scale bar for 4 \times magnification = 200 μ m, scale bar for 40 \times magnification = 20 μ m. I: Counted erythrocytes in the margin area ($n = 5$ –10). Kruskal-Wallis-test and Dunn's multiple comparison analysis. **: p-value <0.01, *: p-value <0.1. J: Counted erythrocytes in the central ROI ($n = 5$ –10). Ns = not significant (Kruskal-Wallis-test and Dunn's multiple comparison analysis). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the prescribing information in human patients (according FDA Prescribing information for Gem, Ref. ID 4433223), Gem is administered at a human dose of max. 1250 mg/m² per day. We converted the dose administered in humans according to Nair and Jacob [53] (see methods Eqn 4 and 5), which results in an estimated equivalent dose of 6 μ mol Gem in the CAM. This value, however, is only a very rough estimate of the order of magnitude of administered drug amount. We therefore chose treatment concentrations spanning a total drug amount of 5 nmol–1 μ mol over five days (daily topical drops of 0.1–10 mM, 10–20 μ L per drop). The theoretical maximum drug load delivered from the GemIP was calculated based on the *post*-CAM delivery rates for devices operated at 100 nA (median = 16.55 pmol/min; Fig. 2A) and results in an average of ca. 119 nmol after 120 h of GemIP operation at 100 nA. The survival of the chick embryos was not impaired compared to the untreated embryos in the groups treated with Gem between 0 and 250 nmol, or the GemIP. However, at a total Gem amount of 500 nmol and 1000 nmol, the toxicity of the treatment was lethal to the host organism (Fig. 4D).

At EDD15 we quantified the diameters of the tumors shown in the dashed lines in Fig. 4E. We established two control groups that were not treated with Gem: growth control (tumor growth without any influence) and the sham ion pump control (installing non-toxic IP devices on tumors in the same fashion as with GemIPs, without operating them). The growth control and the sham ion pump control had a diameter of 1.96 ± 0.76 mm and 2.12 ± 0.76 mm, respectively (Fig. 4F). The topical treatment with 100 nmol and 250 nmol Gem did not interfere with the tumor size and resulted in an average diameter of 1.96 ± 0.24 mm and 2.08 ± 0.37 mm (Fig. 4F). The topical treatment had an anti-angiogenic effect, reducing the vascularization of the tumors which then appeared white due to the lack of blood vessels, but did not hinder the tumors to grow to a size comparable to the growth and sham ion pump control. Strikingly, only the constant treatment with the GemIP at 100 nA over 120 h (ca. 119 nmol) resulted in a relevant inhibition of tumor growth indicated by the significantly reduced mean diameter of 1.24 ± 0.55 mm (Fig. 4F). We also quantified the rate of apoptosis that yielded an increased CC3 in both the topical treatment controls (250 nmol) and the GemIP treated ones after 120 h (Fig. 4G and Suppl. Fig. 13), showing that compared to the untreated control (GC, 0.50% CC3 positive cells) both treatments with 250 nmol Gem metronomically, and with the GemIP significantly upregulated the CC3 positive cells (3.0% and 4.4%, respectively). Furthermore, we quantified proliferating cells within CAM tumors using Ki67 staining. The tumors treated with GemIP and the topical treatment controls (250 nmol) exhibited Ki67 expression levels of $39.64 \pm 7.09\%$ and $42.29 \pm 10.45\%$, respectively, whereas untreated control tumors exhibited $44.98 \pm 4.77\%$ of Ki67-expressing cells (Suppl. Fig. 14).

We furthermore investigated the extent of vascularization of the differently treated tumors. As mentioned, we observed a white appearance of tumors in metronomic treatment controls, while GemIP treated tumors appeared with a pink hue (Fig. 4E). We therefore did a

histological analysis on H&E sections of all tumors, in which blood cells were visualized in pink, while the blue nuclei were desaturated (Fig. 4H, Suppl. Fig. 15). This showed that in the growth controls, strong and pronounced blood vessels are formed, which are evenly distributed over the whole tumor tissue. In comparison, in the metronomic treatment group we observed on one hand reduced blood vessels in the air-tumor margin, as well as many areas with intratumoral bleeding, most likely due to fragile blood vessels. The GemIP treated tumors showed less bleeding but also a trend towards less blood vessels. We therefore quantified the erythrocytes in both the margin and central areas of all tumors (Fig. 4H–J). In the margins of the growth control tumors the erythrocyte count was 136 ± 38 , which was significantly lowered with both treatments. For the 250 nmol metronomic treatment we counted a mean of 63 ± 30 , and in the GemIP tumors we counted a mean of 56 ± 18 erythrocytes (Fig. 4I). In the central area, the count was 108 ± 37 , 85 ± 22 and 70 ± 25 counts for the untreated, 250 nmol metronomically and GemIP treated tumors, respectively, and no significant change was observed between the different groups (Fig. 4J).

These experiments clearly highlight that only GemIP constant treatment managed to interfere with GBM tumor growth. Metronomic Gem treatments, on the other hand, were not able to slow down the overall growth of GBM tumors, although early apoptosis was significantly upregulated. Topical and GemIP treatment also largely diminished the vascularization of GBM tumor surface. The metronomic treatment resulted in a white appearance of the tumors, while the minimal vascularization is apparently sufficient to still foster rapid GBM tumor growth, which only GemIP treatment is able to reduce.

We hypothesize that it is not only the delivered dose of Gem that causes the drastic decrease in tumor size, but the local concentration distribution of the drug in the system over extended periods of time. To investigate these effects more thoroughly, we used a finite element model of the GemIP and operated it in a simulated CAM environment (Fig. 5A). The digital CAM-GemIP model evaluated the GemIP operation itself, the Gem flux over the CAM, and thus the administrated concentration vs. time of the treatment. Overlays in Fig. 5B display the CAM surface within the silicone ring as the target area in which the pharmacokinetic events take place. The two treatment techniques generate very different concentration profiles in both space and time. The simulations of the topical drop treatment generated a high transient Gem concentration which was evenly distributed over the whole ring surface. This topical concentration diminished within 24 h to almost base level (Fig. 5B, C), which is in line with the fading effect we observed in the mass spectrometry-quantified intratumoral drug concentrations (Fig. 2D). The GemIP treatment was able to generate more local drug concentrations around the outlet of an operating GemIP compared to the topical drop treatment (≥ 100 μ M = magenta, Fig. 5B). The corresponding average concentration profile (within the silicone ring area) over 24 h indicates a steady treatment and the buildup of a high local Gem concentration over the first 6 h of GemIP operation, which remains high over the whole operation time (Fig. 5C), a treatment regime that is

Fig. 5. Computer simulations of GemIP and topical treatment on CAM-grown tumors. A: Schematic representation of the CAM simulation environment. B: Simulation of the spatial Gem concentration over the surface in the silicone ring placed on the CAM for Gem administrated via GemIP (1 nmol/h over 24 h), and topical drop administration of Gem onto the CAM (50 nmol added at $t = 0$), indicating the drug concentration gradient within this area at 1 h, 12 h and 24 h after treatment start. C: Simulation of average Gem concentration within the silicone area over 24 h generated by topical drop treatments (1–50 nmol per daily dose resulting in 5–250 nmol over five days), in comparison with continuous treatment of GemIP at 1 nmol/h during the same 24 h period.

superior for tumor growth interference. While the average concentration within the treatment area peaks with initial drug concentration of the topical drop treatment, simulations suggests that the average concentration generated by the GemIP remains below 100 μM within the same area during the entire treatment. As a result, the GemIP can generate an effective and continuous treatment of the GBM tumor, while providing a safer treatment option for surrounding tissue than metronomic topical protocols.

4. Discussion

Local drug delivery techniques represent a paradigm shift in the fight against hard-to-treat tumors. These techniques bring with them a wealth of features favorable for efficiently killing tumor cells: local drug accumulation and confined local drug distributions that render drugs more efficient and less harmful for the system. In the case we present here, it is furthermore possible to gain electronic control over local dosing profiles and pharmacokinetics. Especially with systemic drug administration, the intratumoral drug concentrations are poorly matched with pharmacokinetics, resulting in the case that drugs only transiently reach effective concentrations within the tumor. With iontronic devices, we present a platform that can overcome such limitations and fulfill the promise of effective local chemotherapy. Iontronic devices can be operated effectively at low power in the nanowatt range, which renders this technology highly favorable for translation into fully implantable prototypes in/on the brain or elsewhere in the body. Additionally, iontronic transport facilitates the delivery of potent chemotherapeutic drugs such as Gem into the brain, by overcoming the BBB. This provides the opportunity to utilize potent drugs, previously not considered for brain tumor treatment. With these devices it is possible to generate local and long-lasting drug concentrations, that can be adjusted to levels in the higher, more effective *local* therapeutic window of a specific drug, rather than the *systemic* window determined more by side-effects and toxicity than local efficacy.

We showed the delivery of the potent chemotherapeutic Gem via

iontronic devices incorporating an A-HPG polyelectrolyte as ion conductor and observed that this combination is capable of a stable delivery over three days. Capillary iontronic devices with A-HPG IEM have increased Gem delivery up to ~ 0.4 pmol/min/nA (at 100 nA) in comparison to ~ 0.1 pmol/min/nA (at 20 nA) in our previous work [33]. With certain GemIPs, we observed in this treatment period that the device performance can be hampered due to the operation in the host organism. During the GemIP *in vivo* experiments the chick embryos are constantly and substantially growing, causing movements of the tumor over time. In addition, the beating of the animal heart leads to visible contractions and periodic movement of both the blood vessel and tumor structure. When the *in vivo* tested GemIPs were re-evaluated after 3 and 5 days of operation in the living organism, we observed a ~ 50 –60% decrease in median delivery rates. A potential reason for the decreased delivery rate is that the IEM may have partially dried out during the *in vivo* experiments, likely due to the direct contact with the dense cell layer and the rather dry nature of the CAM where the tumors grew. This potential effect on the IEM likely correlates with the observed increase in resistance during *in vivo* experiments. In future experiments we will evaluate if devices with increased durability [66], together with consistent humidity level in the experimental setup, can overcome these limitations. Other potential explanations for the decreased GemIP performance could be the formation of a foreign body response capsule at the channel outlet, and thus increased ionic transport resistance although no such foreign body response was observed under visual inspection.

Despite these limitations, GemIPs nevertheless generated clearly detectable and physiologically relevant intratumoral drug concentrations which induced significant S-phase cell cycle arrest and induction of apoptosis in the tumors, almost as high as the positive metronomic controls after 3-day treatment. Remarkably, 24 h after the last topical treatment we observed almost completely abolished G₂ phase. As GBM tumors are still growing despite topical metronomic Gem treatment intervention, we expect the growth arrest to be transient. This is in line with a previous work, performing a 6 h treatment of Gem on pancreatic

tumor cells. Here, certain Gem concentrations, inducing only partial apoptosis, resulted in a decreased G₂ phase within the first 24 h, while at later time points tumor cells recovered and had a normal cell cycle [67].

The observations of GemIP treatment on tumor formation and proliferation inspired us to perform extended *in vivo* iontronic drug delivery over five days started just one day after cell seeding, a time point where the tumors are just beginning to form a solid structure. To date this is the longest iontronic drug delivery that has been reported. Especially in the context of tumor growth inhibition, the GemIP outperformed metronomic treatment protocols, despite the fact that topical treatment was administered either at an equal or higher total dose to the tumor and that the overall drug concentration and drug-exposed region is significantly smaller for GemIP delivery. This very efficient growth inhibition is accomplished by the GemIP, which induced early apoptosis to a similar extent as the metronomic treatment with 250 nmol Gem administered topically. Nevertheless, those tumors that had formed and grown despite either the metronomic or GemIP treatment yielded a slight, yet not significant decrease in the proliferation rate, based on Ki67 expression. These experiments on growth inhibition, early apoptosis and proliferation suggest that GemIP treatment interferes most efficiently in the early stage of tumor formation. This strengthens the theory that a low continuous dose is a more efficient treatment option compared to the burst release from the metronomic treatment. In addition, when considering the high survival rate of the chick embryos treated with the GemIPs, we hypothesize that it is possible to increase the dosage and at the same time, stay within the therapeutic window, which can be accomplished by driving a higher current.

For the topical treatment, we observed a drastic decrease in Gem concentration within 3–6 h, diminishing to a 100 times lower concentration than initially detected after treatment start. Hence, a possible explanation is that tumor cells might be able to recover from transient Gem concentrations and are able to overcome the cytotoxic effects. We learned from our previous work that U-87 MG cells still have approximately 50% cell viability at Gem doses in the millimolar range after 72 h *in vitro* [33]. Furthermore, we assume that the administered Gem, once inside the cell, integrates into the DNA of the target cell within less than one hour [59]. It is, however, reported that Gem-treated cells can overcome treatment effects and re-start proliferation surprisingly well once they are no longer exposed to the cytotoxin [68], and we showed in the present work, that the Gem concentration after topical treatment diminishes drastically within 6 h *post* treatment. These facts point to the conclusion that cells exposed to the drug incorporate it rather quickly into their DNA, but might overcome treatment effects once the drug is no longer present.

A major advantage of GemIPs is that while continuous drug delivery generates locally high and constant Gem concentrations at the GemIP outlet, the accumulated systemic drug load is much lower compared to topical treatments and therefore exposes the host organism to a minimal extent. Instead, the drug applied *via* topical treatment imposes a much higher systemic load to the host organism (that even intoxicated the embryonic chick) but decays to almost base level within 6 h after administration in the tumor, as it is cleared *via* the circulation and distributed in the *in vivo* system. This is similar to the administration of drugs intravenously or orally, where a single dose creates a transient concentration peak that decays within 3–6 h in mice and humans after intravenous and oral Gem administration [69,70]. These drug concentration profiles are important indicators that can be the basis for GemIP simulations and to make predictions for GemIP operations and drug accumulation in the future.

Continuous and long-lasting drug presentation is especially favorable in the context of anti-tumor effects [71]. Indeed, the cytotoxic and anti-proliferative effects arising from transient drug presentation can diminish within days [68]. Also, drug penetration depth is highly relevant for the effectiveness of the treatment to achieve cytotoxicity of tumors, which is dependent on the diffusion of the drug, metabolism, and binding in the tissue [71]. Continuous drug infusion improves the

targeted tumor cell death due to slower drug penetration and higher drug retention in the tumors [71,72]. The continuously high drug concentration generated by a GemIP is therefore an additional possible explanation for the successful inhibition of tumor growth of the GemIP-treated GBM tumors.

Metronomic and GemIP treatment also manifested in a similar degree of vascularization reduction of tumors at the margin of the tumor. The CAM facing, central tumor areas of both treatment groups represent a slightly but not significantly decreased, high vascularization, comparable to non-treated GBM tumors. We observe that both the GemIP and the metronomic chemotherapy have clear anti-angiogenic effects and eliminate the dividing endothelial cells of newly forming blood vessels, as reported for metronomic treatment [73]. Yet, the metronomic topical treatment was ineffective in reducing tumor size over the maximum treatment time, while GemIPs were effective to manifest the size effect. We hypothesize that the remaining vasculature, that grows underneath the tumor to an extent comparable to untreated tumors, is still functional and efficient enough to nurture remaining tumor cells so they can proliferate and grow, especially when the tumor is not exposed to the drug during the metronomic treatment. Even in hypoxic conditions (1% O₂), U-87 MG and other glioblastoma cell lines remain their proliferation, but not to the same extent as in normoxic conditions [74,75]. We are aware of characteristics in the GBM tumor microenvironment (TME), such as hypoxic niches, which can be a hub for the development of cancer stem cells, and therefore, want to carefully examine in future in *in vivo* experiments in rodents, whether GemIP treatments cause hypoxic tissue areas and whether they might be unfavorable. These rodent *in vivo* experiments will enable us to furthermore investigate additional effects of GemIP treatments on the TME, which is in GBM especially influenced by immune cells such as macrophages. This TME aspect was not studied in the CAM tumor model, as the host immune system is just developing and immature at the time when experiments are performed.

We conclude from this that both the dosing concentration and local drug profile are critical parameters for the success of the overall tumor treatment, which importantly manifests in the reduction of the tumor size for GemIP treated GBMs grown on CAM. Due to this local and continuous drug dosing, we intend to implement this technology for the treatment of GBM in rodent *in vivo* studies, and eventually in GBM patients after tumor resection. In such human studies, we foresee using GemIPs placed in the resection region after the maximum safe resection of the gross tumor mass, with tumor cells that have infiltrated the healthy brain tissue being the primary target. We thus see GemIPs and other such iontronic devices as becoming promising new tools for patients and neurooncologists to meaningfully intervene with GBM progression and recurrence, while minimizing the total dose and side-effects.

Author contributions

V.H., L.W. and T.A.S. contributed equally to this work. V.H., L.W., T.A.S., T.A., M.S., R. S., S.P., D.T.S. and N.G. conceived of the ideas, supervised the project and interpreted the data. L.W., V.H., T.A.S. and R.S. prepared the original draft of the manuscript. V.H., L.W., S.E., A.G., W. H. J.D. and N.G. conducted CAM experiments. V.H. performed tumor size measurements, as well as IHC, FACS and erythrocyte count analysis. L.W., V.H. and S.E. performed GemIP characterization and operation. T.A.S. implemented and conducted computer simulations. T.A. synthesized the IEM material. T.A., M.S., I.B.W., and H.S. manufactured and characterized the iontronic devices. T.T. and S.H. performed drug quantification and proteomics with MS. S.P. provided primary neuronal cultures. M.A. helped with IHC staining and analysis. R.B.G., U.S. and M. B. contributed to the study design, revised the manuscript and supported data analysis together with all other authors.

Artwork

Renderings of GemIPs were done by Maximilian Schinagl. Schematic illustrations were done in BioRender (purchased license).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Verena Handl: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Linda Waldherr:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Theresia Arbring Sjöström:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tobias Abrahamsson:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Maria Seitanidou:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Sabine Erschen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Astrid Gorischek:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Iwona Bernacka-Wojcik:** Methodology, Investigation. **Helena Saarela:** Methodology, Investigation. **Tamara Tomlin:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sophie Elisabeth Honeder:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Joachim Distl:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Waltraud Huber:** Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Asslaber:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ruth Birner-Grünberger:** Writing – review & editing. **Ute Schäfer:** Writing – review & editing. **Magnus Berggren:** Writing – review & editing. **Rainer Schindl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Silke Patz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Daniel T. Simon:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nassim Ghaffari-Tabrizi-Wizsy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

T.A.S., T.A., M.B., and D.T.S. are shareholders in the small, researcher-controlled intellectual property company OBOE IPR AB (oieipr.com), which owns the patents related to the iontronic technology presented above. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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